

Bacteria

: an Essay

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I am everything because I am just a stream of unhinged life;
I am immortal: every death is within me (...),
 & in me,
gathered together,
 life
is no more divided and determined
 but boundless
 thus, free”

Giuseppe Tomasi di Lampedusa, La Sirena (*)

Bacteria and a new biopolitical project

In the middle of the 19th century, Louis Pasteur, using new optical technologies and positivist theories of sciences made microbes visible for the first time to the human eye. Pasteur put forward a new germ theory, in which microbes were the cause for diseases and putrefaction instead of “miasmas”. Miasmas or “atmospheric impurity” were then thought to “arise from the accumulation in and around their dwellings of the decomposing remnants of the substances used for food and from the impurities given out from their own bodies” – bodies poor people.

The germ theory enabled a new perception of health and disease as pathogens were found to be the direct cause of infectious diseases. Regardless, the moral overtones of the miasmatic theory has never died. The nexus between the scientific thinking of a new technological era and the victorian morality realized fast enough that by changing the environment – and controlling bodies – where microbe lived could influence human health. This is precisely where “microbes” or bacterias deeply influenced cities and design in complex ways since then. The hygienist movement that took over Europe during the second half of the 19th century defined design of spaces as a form of preventive medicine for the body. To this day, public and domestic spaces became a battlefield where the war against “germs” is never ending.

Here I want to explore how microbes dominated cities and design of the industrial and post industrial era through the concept of sterilization. Sterilization as a set of practices, tastes and beliefs that cast our collective imaginaries and deepened the divide between culture and nature to this day. I believe that looking through the lens of sterilization is not only relevant to draw awareness to an one-sided anthropocentric concern with “human health” at the expense of our relationship with other non-human species.

Nevertheless, the divide between human and non-human must change. The need of a new economic paradigm in a resource depleting world is hopefully stimulating the work of thinkers and scientists to reaccess our relationship with “nature”. Above all, by learning how indigenous people from all continents teamed with biological and environmental dynamics to sustain themselves can inform us about new explorations that include mutualism and symbiosis. Such explorations can help us to gain insights for how the building environment can draw new ethical standards through new material “ecologies”, construction practices and how (and to “whom”) we design. The world needs a new “cosmopolitics” (1), new “biopolitic” projects (2), and all land be tended as part of the “planetary garden” (3) to dismantle systems of ecological simplification and commodification of natural resources (4). By learning how bacteria underlie all flows, processes and manifestations of the biosphere is a good starting point.

(1) apud Isabelle Stengers, *Pour en finir avec la tolérance. Cosmopolitiques*, 7. Paris: La Découverte, 1997.

(2) apud P. Viganò, *Le Jardin biopolitique: Espaces, vies et transition*, Ed. METIS PRESS-ES, Lausanne, 2023.

(3) apud Gilles Clément, *Où en est l'herbe?: Réflexions sur le Jardin planétaire*, Ed. ACTES SUD, 2006.

(4) Haraway, Donna. 2015. “Anthropocene, Capitalocene, Plantationocene, Chthulucene: Making Kin.” *Environmental Humanities* 6, no. 1: 159-165.

In this exploration, I want to show how bacteria underlie design and how we plan and have transformed our cities around bacteria. I also want to highlight the work of thinkers like Lynn Margulis and how it has helped to shift our perspective from the neo Darwinian view on life, which is essentially ruthless competition, to the perspective of broad interweaving of mutualistic and symbiotic relationships. I will then discuss new material ecologies that are emerging from novel biotechnologies that see microorganisms as allies and that will potentially build new nexus between material flows (including waste) and design.

Lastly, I will explore the work of practitioners who may shape how we reconsider our relationship with the environment through design. I firmly believe that there is still time to recognize new ways in which we can coexist and thrive with other species and move beyond linear exploitation-fabrication-assembly-disposal industrial logics into an interspecies

The microbes

In the Book “The microbes” (1), Bruno Latour traces the deep social transformation that Pasteur discovered allowed in the second half of the 19th century. More importantly, 19th century hygienism and disease control became crucial to make the European colonial enterprise profitable. As Latour states, “Malaria or yellow fever were to be destroyed not with vaccines but by ordering the colonist and natives to build their homes differently”. The hygienist program was a colonial agenda that targeted that target not only germs, but also cultures. Most importantly, the Hygienist thinking reshaped social links on a new footing to include Pasteur’s discovery, the microbes – not as companions of course – deepening the fracture between men and “nature” in western societies.

(1) Bruno Latour, “Les microbes: guerre et paix”. 2011. Collection : Poche / Sciences humaines et sociales, La Découverte.

In this way, sterilization has become the cornerstone of a political agenda that perfected designing systems for spatial and social control. From European and North American cities this concept rapidly extended to the Global South, intricately linked to colonial economic and political interests. For instance, urban planners and designers introduced infrastructure innovations that enhanced the overall sanitary conditions of cities, yet simultaneously exacerbated social inequalities, beneficial for maintaining a cheap labor force. Industrial districts and working-class neighborhoods were meticulously zoned and designed to maximize efficiency while managing sanitary conditions.

Concurrently, society has become increasingly detached from “natural” biological processes to the extent that we now saturate our homes with poisons and harmful products. This trend can be traced back to the 1884 “Health Exhibition” in London, where middle-class families perused gadgets and products aimed at ensuring the cleanliness and purity of their households. Nowadays, people often rush to stores like Home Depot to purchase broad-spectrum sprays of pesticides and germ killers, inadvertently destroying beneficial bacteria present in their bodies, increasing the risk of succumbing to antibiotic-resistant strains.

How we design our home, of course, has not escaped from the sterilization hysteria. Furniture design was modified – ornaments faded away into sleek and smooth surfaces that dominate design nowadays. In fact, “sterilization design” has become so widespread and refined that most of us have become blind not only to the presence of our companions – the bacteria and an infinitude of other beneficial microorganisms – but also to the strategies that have permitted their invisibilization through the obsession to over-managed landscapes and quasi-medical buildings and interiors.

Think for example of the plasticky surfaces and the widespread use of glazing in our houses – glass is a laboratory material par excellence after all – supporting the delusional fantasy that we can live and thrive apart from other organisms, apart from other non-human beings. Landscapes have often been transformed into plantations of ornamental plants imported from other ecosystems to ensure no local “pest” will thrive on them. Ecosystems simplification is the ultimate defence of western capitalism against germs.

Next page: Advertisement, 1966.
Source: Wikicommons.

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Ecosystems simplification underpins an unending quest for expanding the capital's extractive frontiers. By rendering invisible the non-human being, capitalism is boundless within a world with clear environmental limitations. Richard Sennett in the book "Flesh and Stone" draws attention to this modern socio-ecological dysfunctional relationship, naming it "politics of indifference" – a mechanism that legitimizes the invisibility of the "different" – human or non-human. Not surprisingly, such politics also find resonance in the modern grid plan and zoning of modern cities – in particular American cities. Suburban sprawl is after all only possible since individual parcels of land defined by streets and highways have become commodity – an abstract unit for speculation and capital accumulation without respect for historic uses, social needs and pre existing ecosystems, including Soil and all its micro biodiversity. Soils in modern cities are systematically ignored, dug out, wasted to give place to the life-depleted, sanitized landscapes of the American suburbia.

Previous page: "La Nueva Topographia di Roma", detail, by Giambattista Nolli, 1748. Source: Wikicommons.

“Science has inherited stories about human mastery from the great monotheistic religions. These stories fuel assumptions about human autonomy, and they direct questions to the human control of nature, on the one hand, or human impact on nature, on the other, rather than to species interdependence.”

Anna Tsing, 2012, “Unruly Edges: Mushrooms as Companion Species”, *Environmental Sciences* 1: 141-151.

A bacterial world

But After all, what is a bacterium?

What are the origins of the bacteria?

How does it relate to other living organisms?

Earth has been a bacterial world for at least the last 3.5 billion years. In the oceans of our young planet, bacteria were among the first forms of life to emerge. Long before plants or animals had evolved, bacterial colonies flourished and grew. Talking about bacterial touches the very definition of life.

But let's step back a little more a pose a fundamental question:

What is life? At least as we know it on this planet...

In essence, living beings are entities built on really complex orchestration of chemistry and information management that allows organisms to adapt and persist through inheritance.

Firstly, all life on Earth is based on carbon.

A living thing are separated entities from their environments, yet intrinsically interconnected to them through food/resources.

A living thing have genes and other equipment that ensures that it can process food/resources into energy, grow and reproduce.

A living thing must be able to evolve. That means it develops through natural selection to ensure the of the most able to adapt to environmental changes.

All these attributes of life come down to cellular processes, and bacteria are single cells that preceded more complex cell at the beginning of life on Earth. In fact, bacteria played a crucial role in building up cells complexity found in more complex life forms. But first, what is bacteria and how does it relate to other forms of life on Earth?

Bacteria are the simplest living organisms we think of as being alive. Bacterial cells are filled with a substance called cytoplasm, a concentrated mixture of proteins and nutrients needed for life. A single twisted and compacted loop of DNA carries their genetic code, but they may also have supplementary useful genes in tiny rings called plasmids. Some bacteria have hair-like flagella or tiny retractable pili which enable them to move and to grapple.

Scientists once thought of archaea and bacteria as a single group of organisms. Then in 1977, genetic analysis revealed that archaea had a separate evolutionary history to bacteria and therefore represent an independent branch of life altogether – such simple organisms probably came to being before 3.7 billion years ago. Based on geological evidence, around 2.5 billion years ago, Cyanobacteria living in the oceans evolved the ability to split water using energy from the Sun. Through this process, called photosynthesis, they began producing oxygen as a by-product, marking the Great Oxygenation Event. The bacteria's waste product, oxygen, permanently changed the make-up of the seas and atmosphere. This set the scene for complex life to develop.

But what how does bacteria relate to other forms of life?

Left: Endosymbiosis theory proposed by Lynn Margulis in which the mitochondrion and the chloroplast are both organelles that were once free-living cells (prokaryotes) that ended up evolving together with their host cells, creating complex cells capable of producing energy. The resulting symbiotic relationship produced complex cells of multicellular organisms. Source: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1161-5_4

In 1967, Lynn Margulis (then Lynn Sagan) published an article entitled “On the Origin of Mitosing Cells” in the Journal of Theoretical Biology. This publication did not have an auspicious beginning, reportedly having been rejected by more than a dozen journals before eventually finding a home. In her paper, Margulis posed a theory known as endosymbiosis claiming that eukaryotic cells – cells with a nucleus that divide by classical mitosis, and found in all plants and animals, but not bacteria – were first formed billions of years ago when one single-celled organism – a prokaryote – engulfed another to create a new type of cell.

So what happened in the earliest evolution of these crucial cells? Initially, one bacterium ate a different, oxygen-using bacterium but didn't digest it. Over time the two became interdependent and the bacterium took over almost all of the energy-generating processes of the host cell, becoming what we now call a mitochondrion. This allowed the cell to evolve into bigger cells and eventually form communities and develop into multicellular organisms.

This theory brought her into conflict with other researchers, including the so-called neo-Darwinists who believed in slow and continuous step-wise evolution driven by competition between organisms. Needless to say, however, that Margulis theory also brought a different lens on how cooperation and not competition and predation have shaped life on this planet. More importantly, it suggested that bacteria had a central role on the evolution of complex lifeforms and planetary ecology – In other words, the planet as we know today is only possible due to the intermingling of bacteria with other organisms shaping the very fabric of life.

For example, the uptake of nutrients by plants is possible not only by the presence of mycelium networks and bacteria in the soil that recycle and make nutrients available to the plants, but also by the presence of bacteria within plants cellular structure.

Recent studies have shown that Plants host distinct bacterial communities associated with roots and the leaf surface and inside various plant organs. Such plant microbiota is as a fundamental trait that includes mutualism between plants and bacteria, enabling diverse biochemical mechanisms that control plant growth, nutrient uptake and resilience against heat and drought.

There is still a multitude of mechanisms between plants and bacteria that are still unknown; regardless, it's been long known that chemical fertilization and pesticides used in the industrial agriculture destroy not only the soil but also the plant microbiota, impacting the nutritional value of food – It is not surprising that human diet based on processed food and produce from industrial agriculture is directly related to diabetes and obesity, likely due to unhealthy gut microbiome. It is safe to say that like, plants, human health is largely supported by biochemical processes from our own body microbiome.

Symbiotic relationships between plant roots and bacteria. Drawings by the author, based in Ambrosini et al. 2016. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-015-2727-7

Bacterial cultures

The symbiosis between bacteria and multicellular life goes beyond metabolic processes, and fell into the domain of culture early on in human history. Among countless ancient foods that relied on bacteria and yeast (a fungus), like beer, wine, kimchi, sauerkraut, miso and other fermented foods, fermented milk, like yogurt, sour creams and kefir, is probably one of the oldest and fascinating use of bacteria in human diet.

Yogurt is the product of lactic acid bacteria present naturally in milk and human saliva that digest (or ferment) the milk sugar lactose. As a by-product of fermentation, this kind of bacteria produce lactic acid, and in doing so, they create a unique ecosystem for themselves. Pathogenic bacteria are killed or inhibited by these weak acids, but the manipulation of lactic acid bacteria go beyond milk preservation, and has nutritional consequences like the increasing of vitamin levels that probably allowed human populations to migrate across continents during the Holocene.

The fermentation of milk would have been essential for these early farmers, who are known to have lacked the genetic ability to digest the milk sugar lactose as adults. The evolutionary origin of the bacteria present in fermented milk is also fascinating. For example, genetic evidence suggests that *Streptococcus thermophilus*, an important yogurt bacteria that grows best near body temperature, likely evolved from *Streptococcus salivarius* or *Streptococcus vestibularis*, two closely related species found in human saliva, which suggests that saliva microbes colonized yoghurts and evolved to thrive in the conditions the yoghurt presented.

Rock art from the 5th millennium BC northern Africa, a time during which humans still relied on cattle, show that sheep and goats were a stable and widespread way of life, long before the first evidence for domesticated plants or settled village farming communities. An article (1) discussing these paintings, states “The extensive rock art demonstrates that cattle played an important part in the lives and ideology of ancient human groups living in this region during the Holocene. This pictorial record contains countless scenes with representations of cattle, some emphasizing the female’s full udders and, in a few cases, depictions of the actual milking of a cow”. The article also described the DNA sequencing of ceramic shards containing organic matter remains, including lipid biomarkers derived from degraded animal fats and components of bacterial origin.

(1) Dunne et al. First dairying in green Saharan Africa in the fifth millennium BC. *Nature*, 2012, vol. 486.

Line drawing after Rock Art, northern Africa. Source: doi:10.1038/nature11186

Even in cultures that didn't rely on milk as a staple food, like in the nowadays "Americas", were fermenting plants and roots into beverages with strong cultural significance.

For example, indigenous people across the "Americas" were making what in Tupi – the language of the people who used to live along the Atlantic coast of South America before European invasion – is called "Cauim" (but has different names in other indigenous languages, i.e., chicha), a beverage made by fermenting manioc, maize, or plantains.

The starting material was cooked in large ceramic pots, chewed, and fermented, so that enzymes (including amylase) present in human saliva could break down the starch into fermentable sugars. This preparation was originally used for Japanese sake.

Jean de Léry, 1578.
Histoire d'un voyage
fait en la terre du
Brésil, autrement
dite Amerique.
Source: Wikicom-
mons

Straw weaving by Baniwa people, northern Brazil. The imagery represents a flock of birds, but also symbolizes how “nature” is entangled with humans. Personal collection, unknown date.

Bacteria & Culture, Nature & Culture

Planetary social–ecological transformations are dynamic – in the sense that human interventions are now entangled with all systems of the biosphere – climate, terrestrial and oceanic systems – in a scale never seen. Humans are not separated from nature. We’ve never been. And technologies are tools for transforming nature into manmade nature.

Nevertheless, Capital has been appropriating nature and transforming nature in an unending quest to produce more commodities at the expense of cheap human labor (including enslaved human labor) and unpaid work of non–human living beings. Now these transformations happen at the cellular scale to deploy benefits to humans – we have started by producing the GMOs a few decades now, after all.

CRISPR (1) has gained a lot of attention recently as a result of debate among scientists about the possibility of genetically modifying the human genetic code and the ethical implications of doing so. I want to step back from this ethical issue in which science defines the boundaries of science and calls out for vague players such as “the scientific community” and “society” (2). But I’m afraid no one is listening – instead, science has deployed a tool that is out there to be used by exploiting nature services. The logics of intentional biological transformation (i.e., gene editing) sounds like an exciting novel technology, but it’s actually an old one – it is Plantation. Plantation seeks for ecological simplification.

Plantations are the most “ugly blueprint” of capital expropriation of environments. Plantations, arguably, provided perfected the mechanized factory production system creating “devastating transformations of diverse kinds,” (3) sparked through ecological simplification and displacement of habitats and people. What would be the consequences of expanding the plantation logics to now design living organisms by editing their genetic code to deliver “benefits” to humans?

(1) Ran, F., Hsu, P., Wright, J. et al. Genome engineering using the CRISPR–Cas9 system. *Nat Protoc* 8, 2281–2308 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2013.143>

(2) e.g. C. Brokowski, M. Adli, CRISPR Ethics: Moral Considerations for Applications of a Powerful Tool, *J. Mol. Biol.* (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2018.05.044>

(3) Haraway, Donna. 2015. “Anthropocene, Capitalocene, Plantationocene, Chthulucene: Making Kin.” *Environmental Humanities* 6, no. 1: 159–165.

“Any science that conceived of the world as being governed according to a universal theoretical plan that reduces its various riches to the drab applications of general laws thereby becomes an instrument of domination. And man, a stranger to the world, sets himself up as its masters.”

Isabelle Stengers, *A Dehumanized World, Order out of Chaos*, 1984.

New Bacterial Cultures: New Material Ecologies

Contrary to other plant-based biomaterials, bacterial biomaterials can be produced worldwide in different climates and using waste from various industries, requiring small laboratory footprints. Bacterial metabolism transforms biomass into by-products, preventing the release of greenhouse gases.

Currently, bacterial materials for construction applications include cellulose and “living” cements obtained through the hydrolysis of urea to produce calcium carbonate. Nevertheless, new “material ecologies” – a speculation of another kind of future – represent a potential alternative to moving away from the age of machinery and massive ecological footprints of industries based on the exploitation of natural resources.

In these new “ecologies,” materials would emerge from the symbiosis of biological processes with waste materials or through the mutualism between synthetic materials and biomaterials to obtain materials with unique mechanical properties. For example, human urine could be used to produce bio-bricks on-site, instead of “wasting” human-produced waste through massive infrastructure (1); thus, bacterial processes could address issues of infrastructure decentralization and waste stream management in cities. Or 3D-printed polymers receive bacteria + nutrients to produce bio-cements, resulting in enhanced mechanical properties (2). Another current exploration is the use of bacteria for biopigments.

(1) S.E. Lambert, D.G. Randall. *Water Research* 160 (2019): 158–166.

(2) Xin et al. Growing living composites with ordered microstructures and exceptional mechanical properties. *Advanced Materials*, vol. 33 (13), April 1, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202006946>

Left: Bionic mineralized composites with selective mineralization. A) Computer-aided design (CAD) models for polymer scaffolds. B) 3D-printed polymer scaffolds. C) Bionic mineralized composite samples. D) Stiffness mapping of the bionic mineralized composites. Source: Xin et al. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202006946>

Ecology of materials highlight site-specific, diversified patterns of relations between materials and bio-chemical processes to “fabricate” new materials.

Bio-based processes: create new materials from wastestream, transform existing materials and compost used materials into resources (bio-chemical composting).

Example: the use of human urine + nutrients from food waste + crushed concrete from construction waste stream to produce bio-bricks.

PURPLE

Janthinobacterium lividum

Janthinobacterium lividum an aerobic soil-dwelling bacterium - it produces various shades of purple pigments due to violacein, which is produced when glycerol is metabolized as a carbon source.

RED

Arthrobacter agilis

Arthrobacter agilis is found in subglacial lakes in the Hymalayas and in Antarctic sea ice, but also found as a pink dusty patina on ancient marble sculptures. The pigment produced by *A. agilis* is spectroscopically identical to a carotenoid-like pigment, and occur in low-lighting and saline environments.

YELLOW

Micrococcus luteus

Micrococcus luteus is an obligate aerobe, pigmented, saprotrophic bacterium found in soil, air and water, and as part of the normal microbiota of mammalian skin. In humans, this bacterium also colonizes upper digestive and respiratory tract. *M. luteus* colonies was recovered from a 120Ma amber, having survived millions of years by processing terpene-related compounds.

INDIGO

Corynebacterium glutamicum

C. glutamicum, a soil bacteria, is one of the leading industrial microorganisms, mainly for producing monosodium glutamate (MSG). *E. glutamicum* has been metabolically engineered to produce high yields of indigoidine by extracting indigoidine synthetase (bpsA) gene from *Streptomyces lavendulae* into *C. glutamicum*, which carries strong fluxes toward l-glutamate, a precursor of indigoidine.

PURPUREA (TYRIAN PURPLE)

Escherichia coli

Commonly found in the gut biome of warm-blooded organisms, but can found in a variety of media. *E. coli* uses mixed acid fermentation in anaerobi conditions to produce lactate, succinate, ethanol, acetate and CO₂. *E. coli* has been used to biosyntheses 6,6'-dibromoindigo, a component only produced by Mediterranean snails - 12,000 snails are needed to produce 1.4g of dye.

BLUE

Streptomyces coelicolor

Streptomyces coelicolor is a soil-dwelling bacterium able to degrade complex organic molelules (chitin, cellulose) and N-fixation with non-legume species *Frankia* sp. *S. coelicolor* produces geosmin, an earthy-smelling substance. As most Actinomycetes, *S. coelicolor* has an unique life cycle during which forms mycelium-like structures and spores, analogous to fungi.

Example of different bacteria currently used for dyeing, tackling one of the most polluting industries: textiles production and dyeing. More in A. Kramar and M. Kostic, Bacterial Secondary Metabolites as Biopigments for Textile Dyeing. Textiles 2022, 2(2), 252-264; <https://doi.org/10.3390/textiles2020013>

“We are addicted to modernity. Most inventions are an attempt by us, humans, to project ourselves into the world beyond our bodies. This gives us an illusion of power, of permanence, the illusion that we will continue to exist. Modernity has those kind of tricks.”

Ailton Krenak, *Life is not useful*, 2023

New Bacterial Cultures: a new Biopolitics

New developments in bacteria-based biomaterials still have limited application in construction. Despite the contemporary fascination with novel biomaterial technologies, most design processes and new propositions seem to be still deeply interwoven with processes that require heavy material transformations and forms with tight connections with function. In other words, heavy fabrication and assembly logics of linear economy. A more open exploration of how we build and dwell, however, could allow alternative routes to design interventions. A route in which bacteria and below ground microorganisms are not just deployed to source materials, but become the foundation and boundaries from which new building and urban forms can emerge.

For example, Fuminori Nousaku from Japan, who is deeply preoccupied about how we dwell on the landscape, proposes new building forms that allow other organisms to thrive by simple design changes. Fuminori understands that if we allow “wild urbanism” through soil-focused design to occur, biodiversity will follow.

The architect states that “We see architecture as part of a large mesh. Buildings are temporary nexus points from resource to disposal. In cities, waste can also become a material. Stripping the asphalt turns the soil into a small production and decomposition field. Solar heat brings cooking out of the kitchen. Lifting a building creates a habitat for living organisms. In this way, life intertwines with the resources around us: sun, soil, and waste. Multispecies networks are established. Just like how microorganisms live in a mesh of decay and regeneration” (1).

Practitioners in the past have highlighted the preoccupation of how urban soils, which is home to a staggering biodiversity, including bacteria, has been treated as blank slate for building on. In the late 1980s, Bernardo Secchi published a thought-provoking article titled *Progetto di Suolo* (A Soil Project) in the *Casabella* magazine (2). Secchi argued that urban soils in the 20th century were not adequately conceptualized, represented, or projected in urban planning. He emphasized the importance of understanding the spatial and functional dimensions of soil to fully grasp modern cities, suggesting that it should be considered a new paradigm for urban projects. Paola Viganò, urbanist and Secchi’s student, made this provocation core to her practice by proposing a series of “requalification” of existing urban forms that allow an “ecological transitioning” (3). These changes in the urban form include reducing impervious surfaces, optimizing green spaces to mitigate habitat fragmentation, and allow the cultivation of parcels of green areas. More importantly, by recognizing that urbanization may increase social inequalities, Viganò incorporates mixed use areas in her “requalification” projects to stimulate participatory governance. Her practice highlights the need for shifting towards a collaborative approach that involves community-based initiatives and collective responsibility to manage the commons, which she calls “a new biopolitics project”. Finally, recognizing the fragility and potential of living soils thriving with beneficial bacteria, is recognizing the building environment as “human-influence nature”.

(1) F. Nousaku and M. Tsuneyama. 2023. *Urban Wild Ecology*. Ed. Toto, Tokyo, Japan.

(2) B. Secchi, *Progetto di suolo*, *Casabella* (1986) pp. 19-23.

(3) P. Viganò, *Le Jardin biopolitique: Espaces, vies et transition*, Ed. METIS PRESSES, Lausanne, 2023.

Fuminori Nousaku

Fuminori Nousaku, Akeno Raised Floor ©Foto Tibor Joanelly, Jumpe Suzuki

Werkvortrag
Mittwoch 25. Oktober, 18.00 Uhr
Raum 3120

(Previous pages)
F. Nousaku
programmes for
forms that do not
harm the soil and its
biodiversity. Source:
<https://www.arced.tum.de/>

Collage from P. Vignolo, *Le Jardin biopolitique: Espaces, vies et transition*, Ed. METIS PRESSES, Lausanne, 2023.

Epilogue

The bacterial world and its symbiotic relationships are the foundation for overcoming the current environmental and climatic crises. Bacterial multiplicity and rhizomatic relations challenge modernity to overcome an unloving relationship with “the other”. This other is “nature”.

We need, however, to embrace the rhizomatic and the symbiotic in opposition to the “one”: the one-world of modernity bases itself on predatory relationships with other non-human living beings. Modernity should instead develop a novel “cosmopolitics” (1), in which society incorporates a multitude of non-human living beings and thus heals a broken relationship with the environment based on the division between humans (culture) and non-humans (nature): We need to break the logic that is breaking the planet; We can start off by recognizing our role within the flows of nature, rather than colonizing and exploiting nature by submitting other nonhuman beings to our own needs; By tending the world as a “planetary garden”, we can intermingle with the myriad of nonhuman beings, “earth-others”, whose flows and needs, like our own, should be acknowledged:

Our practices need to dismantle structures that harm living systems, including bacteria.

(1) Stengers, I. 1997. *Cosmopolitiques VII: Pour en finir avec la tolérance*. Paris: La Découverte, Les Empêcheurs de penser en rond.

Photographs and drawings by
Rodrigo D. Lima.

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